

Synthesis and antimicrobial activity of bis(imido) Schiff bases derived from thiosemicarbazide with some 2-hydroxyaldehydes and metal complexes

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Schiff bases have been synthesised by the reaction of salicylaldehyde, 5-bromosalicylaldehyde, 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde and naphthaldehyde with thiosemicarbazide. The ligands of *N,N'*-bis(salicylidene)thiosemicarbazide (1) react with Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Hg^{II} metals to yield 1 : 1 metal-ligand complexes. The structures of ligands and complexes have been investigated by elemental analyses, magnetic susceptibility measurements, ¹H NMR, IR and UV-visible spectral data. The pentadentate nature of the ligands is inferred from IR spectra. The UV-visible spectral data suggest octahedral geometry for Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, square-pyramidal geometry for Zn^{II} and Hg^{II}. The antimicrobial activities of the ligands and metals complexes have been screened *in vitro* against the organisms *Escherichia coli* ATCC 11230, *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 6538 P, *Bacillus cereus* ATCC 7064, *Proteus vulgaris* ATCC 8427, *Salmonella typhimurium* DSM 554, *Corynebacterium xerosis* ATCC 373 and *Hanseniaspora guilliermondii* DSM 3432, *Rhodotorula rubra* DSM 70403 and *Kluyveromyces fragilis* ATCC 8608. It is observed that the coordination of metal ions has pronounced effect on the microbial activities of the ligands. The metal complexes have higher antimicrobial effect than the free ligand.

Bis(imido) symmetrical and unsymmetrical multidentate Schiff base ligands and their complexes have been synthesized¹⁻⁷. Schiff base complexes are once again topical in connection with a diverse range of applications such as, in organic synthesis⁸⁻¹¹, as liquid crystal¹² and as heterogeneous catalysis¹³. The mono(imido) Schiff base ligands and their complexes derived from the reaction of salicylaldehyde, 5-bromosalicylaldehyde¹⁴ and 2-hydroxyacetophenone¹⁵ with thiosemicarbazide and antifungal properties¹⁴ have been extensively studied. But bis(imido) thiosemicarbazide Schiff base ligands and their complexes have not been studied extensively. They may possess interesting structural features and biological activities. Therefore, the bis(imido) unsymmetrical multidentate Schiff base ligands have been synthesized from salicylaldehyde, 5-bromosalicylaldehyde, 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde and naphthaldehyde with thiosemicarbazide and the complexes of *N,N'*-bis(salicylidene)thiosemicarbazide (1) with Mn^{II} (1a), Co^{II}, (1b), Ni^{II}, (1c), Cu^{II} (1d) and Zn^{II} (1e) and Hg^{II} (1f) have been synthesized and characterized (Scheme 1). The antimicrobial activities of the ligands and metal complexes

have been screened *in vitro* against the following microorganisms : *Escherichia coli* ATCC 11230, *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 6538 P, *Bacillus cereus* ATCC 7064, *Proteus vulgaris* ATCC 8427, *Salmonella typhimurium* DSM 554, *Corynebacterium xerosis* ATCC 373, *Hanseniaspora guilliermondii* DSM 3432, *Rhodotorula rubra* DSM 70403 and *Kluyveromyces fragilis* ATCC 8608 by disc diffusion method^{16,17}.

Results and discussion

The elemental analyses suggest that all the complexes correspond to 1 : 1 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry (Table 1).

Magnetic properties :

The room temperature magnetic data show the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes to be paramagnetic. The μ_{eff} values show the presence of three and two unpaired electrons respectively, indicating the +2 state of Co and Ni. In the case of Co, the usual formation of a tris-chelate and oxidation to +3 state imparting a diamagnetic character to the complex do not take place. This may be due to the steric factor¹⁸.

Scheme 1

Thus the ligands may force Co to remain in the +2 state. In the case of Ni^{II} complexes, the μ_{eff} values are lower than the expected ones (2.84 B.M.). This decrease may be due to the antiferromagnetic exchange between the two nickel atoms. The Mn^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes are diamagnetic and hence suggesting a strong antiferromagnetic coupling interaction between the two manganese and copper centers through the ligands by the super-exchange mechanism. The diamagnetic character of the complexes indicates that the

ground state is the singlet ($S = 0$) and the excited state is the triplet state ($S = 1$)¹⁹.

IR spectra :

The infrared spectra of compounds 1, 2, 3 and 4 show bands at 1617, 1612, 1627 and 1626 cm⁻¹ respectively for $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$, 3443 and 3320, 3456 and 3254, 3423 and 3322 and 3451 and 3258 cm⁻¹ for $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ and N-H indicating the Schiff bases formation. The $\nu_{\text{Ar-H}}$ absorption bands are observed at 3175, 3163, 3070 and 3167 cm⁻¹ for compounds

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of complexes*

Compd.	Colour	M.p. (°C)	Metal% : Found(Calcd.)	μ_{eff} B.M.
[MnL] ₂ (1a)	Yellow	243 (Decomp.)	15.01 (15.60)	Diam.
[CoL] ₂ (1b)	Dark brown	248 (Decomp.)	16.15 (16.54)	4.10
[NiL] ₂ (1c)	Green	254	16.25 (16.50)	2.18
[CuL] ₂ (1d)	Greenish brown	240	17.70 (17.61)	Diam.
[ZnL] (1e)	Yellow	229	17.95 (18.04)	Diam.
[HgL] (1f)	Orange	198	41.55 (40.31)	Diam.

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analysis.

1, 2, 3 and 4. The observation of phenolic $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ at 1338 and 1332 cm^{-1} for **3** and **4** are the evidence for the existence of the keto-amine form (N-H...O intramolecular hydrogen bonding) only in the solid state. The $\nu\text{C}=\text{S}$ stretching bands are observed at 1062–858, 1080–871, 1095–836 and 1108–882 cm^{-1} respectively. The IR spectra of these compounds do not display the $\nu\text{S}-\text{H}$ mode at about 2600 cm^{-1} indicating that in the solid state these ligands remain in the thio-keto form (Scheme 2).

IR spectra of the complexes indicate that Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Hg^{II} are coordinated to the inner N₃O₂ compartment. The $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ and $\nu\text{C}-\text{N}$ vibrations, which appear at 1617 and 1541 cm^{-1} , respectively, in the case of free ligands (**1**), are shifted to 1612–1535, 1602–1537, 1608–1563, 1616–1558, 1606–1538 and 1603–1557 cm^{-1} , respectively, in these complexes.

Electronic spectra :

The UV-vis spectra of ligands **1, 2, 3,** and **4** and complexes **1a, 1b, 1c, 1d, 1e** and **1f** were studied in DMSO. The UV-vis spectra of Schiff bases are studied in polar and non polar solvents²⁰. In polar solvents, a new band at >400 nm is observed that is not found in non polar solvents. The

results indicate that the absorption band at >400 nm belongs to the keto-amine form of the Schiff base^{4,21,22}. The compound **1** and **2** do not show any absorption in the range >400 in DMSO. For compounds **3** and **4**, a new band are observed at >400 nm in the same solvent. Only phenol-imine tautomer is dominant in DMSO for **1** and **2**. On the other hand, the compounds **3** and **4** are in tautomeric equilibria (phenol-imine, O-H...N \rightleftharpoons keto-amine, O...H-N forms) in DMSO (Scheme 3). These tautomers are observed in DMSO for **3** and **4** as supported by ¹H NMR and UV-visible data. The keto-amine tautomer is observed 18% and 24% for compounds **3** and **4** in DMSO.

The Co^{II} complex shows absorptions at 23474 and 38167 cm^{-1} . The absorption at 33333 cm^{-1} is assigned to cobalt-cobalt interaction²³. Thus the local symmetry around each cobalt is octahedral considering the metal-metal interaction. The Ni^{II} complex absorptions at 29498 and 38610 cm^{-1} . Each nickel is octahedral similar to the cobalt complexes. The electronic spectrum of the Mn^{II} complex shows two bands at 29761 and 38461 cm^{-1} . The local symmetry around each manganese may be octahedral considering the manganese-manganese interaction. The Cu^{II} complex show absorptions at 25316 cm^{-1} indicating a square-planar geometry²⁴. It also show absorptions at 32154 and 37878 cm^{-1} indicating the binuclear copper^{II} and dimeric structures²³. The Zn^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes have assigned to distorted square-pyramidal geometry based on their absorptions. The former shows absorptions at 30674–38167 cm^{-1} and 27932–29940–31347–33898–40816 cm^{-1} .

¹H NMR spectra :

The ¹H NMR data of compounds **1, 2, 3** and **4** are given in synthetic procedures. In the ¹H NMR spectra of the compounds **1** and **2** show that the tautomeric equilibrium favours the phenol-imine in DMSO. However, compounds **3** and **4** shifts to the keto amine form in the same solvent. The OH

protons are observed at δ 11.38 and 9.59 ppm singlets, 11.42 and 10.25 ppm singlets, 11.53 singlet and 10.29 doublet ($^3J_{\text{CHNH}}$ 1.85 Hz), 11.40 singlet and 10.11 doublet ($^3J_{\text{CHNH}}$ 7.38 Hz) for ligands **1**, **2**, **3** and **4**. The azomethine protons are observed as singlets 8.36 and 7.93, 8.28 and 8.21 for **1** and **2** and 8.40 ppm doublet (-CS-N=CH-Ar, $^3J_{\text{CHNH}}$ 2.85 Hz) and 8.34 ppm singlet (-HN-N=CH-Ar), 9.04 ppm singlet (-HN-N=CH-Ar) and 8.52 doublet (-CS-N=CH-Ar, $^3J_{\text{CHNH}}$ 7.38 Hz) for **3** and **4**. According to the D₂O exchange spectrum of the ligands **1**, **2**, **3** and **4**, the N-H protons appear as singlets 8.11, 8.17, 8.84 and 8.23 ppm, respectively.

Screening for antimicrobial activities :

Escherichia coli ATCC 11230, *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 6538 P, *Bacillus cereus* ATCC 7064, *Proteus vulgaris* ATCC 8427, *Salmonella typhimurium* DSM 554, *Corynebacterium xerosis* ATCC 373 and *Hanseniaspora guilliermondii* DSM 3432, *Rhodotorula rubra* DSM 70403 and *Kluyveromyces fragilis* ATCC 8608 were used as bacteria and yeast cultures. The compounds dissolved in DMSO (dimethyl sulfoxide) to a final concentration of 30 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. Empty sterilized antibiotic discs having a diameter of 6 mm (Schleicher & Schull No 2668, Germany) were each impregnated with 20 μL of solution. All the bacteria mentioned above were incubated at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ for 24 h by inoculation into Nutrient Broth (Difco), and the yeasts studied were incubated in Malt Extract Broth (Difco) for 48 h. An inoculum containing 10^6 bacterial cells or 10^8 yeast cells/mL was spread on Mueller-Minton Agar (Oxoid) plates (1 mL inoculum/plate). The discs injected with solutions were placed on the inoculated agar by pressing slightly and incubated at 35° (24 h) for bacteria, and at 25° (72 h) for yeast. On each plate on appropriate reference antibiotic disc was applied depending on the test microorganisms^{16,17}. The data reported in Table 2 are the average data of three ex-

periments.

Table 2 shows antimicrobial activities of compounds. Besides, the inhibition zones formed by standard antibiotic discs are indicated in Table 3. As can clearly be seen from Table 2, all compound show antimicrobial activity against the test microorganisms used in this study. In classifying the antibacterial activity as Gram (+) or Gram (-), it would generally expected that a much greater number would be active against Gram (+) than Gram (-) bacteria²⁶. However, in this study, the compounds were active against both Gram (+) and Gram (-) bacteria and were highly active against yeasts. The activity against both types of bacteria and yeasts may be inactive of the presence of broad spectrum. When the results obtained were compared to those of standard antibiotics, it was determined that compound **1d** has higher antimicrobial effect against all tested microorganisms. *Staphylococcus aureus* is more susceptible to the compounds **1e** and **1d**, as compared to the standard antibiotics. *Escherichia coli* is resistant and the other microorganisms are seen to be more susceptible to all compounds except for the compounds **1c** and **4**. Similarly, *Salmonella typhimurium* and *Proteus vulgaris* are resistant to the compounds **4**, **2** and **1e**, respectively. The compounds show different effect against used test yeasts. Antimicrobial of the compound **1d** against *Kluyveromyces fragilis*, *Rhodotorula rubra* and *Hanseniaspora guilliermondii* is equivalent, as compared to standard antibiotic Nystatin.

The compounds differ significantly in their activity against tested microorganisms in this study. These differences may be attributed to the fact that the cell wall in Gram (+) bacteria is of a single layer, whereas the Gram (-) cell wall is multi-layered structure and the yeast cell wall is quite complex²⁷.

Table 2. Antimicrobial activity of the compounds

Comps.	1	2	3	4	1a	1b	1c	1d	1e	1f
<i>S. aureus</i>	8	13	8	9	8	8	11	27	16	13
<i>E. coli</i>	8	9	8	-	13	13	-	11	11	9
<i>B. cereus</i>	10	13	10	12	12	12	12	28	11	9
<i>S. typhimurium</i>	10	-	8	-	9	9	11	10	12	13
<i>P. vulgaris</i>	18	12	13	14	11	8	17	21	-	14
<i>C. xerosis</i>	12	12	10	-	14	11	10	21	12	15
<i>K. fragilis</i>	11	-	10	-	13	14	10	18	14	12
<i>R. rubra</i>	16	10	-	-	10	13	11	18	17	14
<i>H. guilliermondii</i>	12	10	-	-	11	12	12	16	18	15

Inactive (-), moderately active (8-13); higher active (>14).

Includes diameter of disc (6 mm).

Table 3. Antimicrobial activities of some standard antibiotics

Microorganisms	Inhibition zone (mm)				
	P10	CTx30	VA30	SAM20	NY100
<i>S. aureus</i>	13	12	13	16	-
<i>E. coli</i>	18	10	22	12	-
<i>B. cereus</i>	14	14	18	16	-
<i>S. typhimurium</i>	13	13	18	12	-
<i>P. vulgaris</i>	10	18	20	14	-
<i>C. xerosis</i>	14	15	18	14	-
<i>K. fragilis</i>	-	-	-	-	18
<i>R. rubra</i>	-	-	-	-	18
<i>H. guilliermondii</i>	-	-	-	-	21

P10 : Penicillin G (10 units), CTx30 : Cefotaxime 30 μg , VA30 : Vancomycin 30 μg , SAM 20 : Ampicillin 10 μg , NY100 : Nystatin 100 μg .

Conclusion :

The Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes are dimeric. The Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes have distorted octahedral structure with metal-metal interaction. The Zn^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes have square-pyramidal structures.

This study is a preliminary evaluation of antimicrobial activity of bis(imido) Schiff bases and metal complexes. It indicates that the compounds have the potential to generate novel metabolites. The compounds show broad spectrum activities. It is observed that the coordination of metal ions has pronounced effect on the bacterial activities of the ligands. The metal complexes have higher antimicrobial activity than the free ligand. The compounds demonstrating broad spectrum activities, may help to discover new antibiotics that could serve as selective agents for the maintenance of animal or human health of infectious diseases.

Experimental

Magnetic susceptibility was determined at RT by Gouy method using EM50 type of control systems and devices using Hg[Co(CNS)₄] as standard; necessary diamagnetic corrections were applied. C, H and N analyses were performed on a LECO CHNS-932 C-, H-, N-, S analyser. Melting points were measured on a Electrothermal A9100 apparatus using a capillary tube. IR absorption spectra were obtained from a Perkin-Elmer RX-II FTIR spectrometer in KBr discs and were reported in cm⁻¹ units. UV-visible spectra were measured using a Shimadzu 160A spectrophotometer in DMSO. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded with a Bruker DPXFT-NMR spectrometer (400 MHz, Me₄Si as internal standard). Salicylaldehyde, 5-bromosalicylaldehyde, 5-nitro salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde, methanol, DMSO, THF, Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Hg^{II} chloride were purchased from Merck (Germany).

Synthetic procedures :

N,N'-Bis(2-hydroxybenzylidene)thiosemicarbazide (1) :

Thiosemicarbazide (0.528 g; 5.79 × 10⁻³ mol) was added to a dry THF (100 ml) solution of salicylaldehyde (1.413 g; 11.580 × 10⁻³ mol). The mixture was stirred and heated for 6 h. On evaporation of THF compound (1) was obtained. It was crystallized from methanol as a yellow solid, m.p. 232°, 0.912 g (53%) yield (Found : C, 59.98; H, 4.11; N, 14.10. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₃N₃O₂S : C, 60.20; H, 4.35; N, 14.05%); ν_{max} (KBr, cm⁻¹) 3443m νO-H, 3320m νN-H, 3175m νArH, 1617s νC=N, 1541s νC-N, 1062s, 858s νC=S; ¹H NMR (DMSO) δ ppm 11.38 (1H, s, OH-Ar-CH=N-NH-), 9.59 (1H, s, OH-Ar-CH=N-CS-), 8.36 (1H, s, -HN-N=CH-Ar), 8.11 (1H, s, -HN-N=CH-Ar), 7.93 (1H, s, -CS-N=CH-Ar), 6.94-7.90 (8H, m, Ar-H).

N,N'-Bis(2-hydroxy-5-bromobenzylidene)thiosemicarbazide (2) :

Thiosemicarbazide (0.018 g, 1.975 × 10⁻⁴ mol) was added to a dry THF (100 ml) solution of salicylaldehyde (0.08 g, 3.98 × 10⁻⁴ mol). Compound (2) was obtained as like (1). White solid, m.p. 241°, 0.05 g (56%) yield (Found : C, 39.01; H, 2.38; N, 8.99. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₁N₃O₂SBr₂ : C, 39.40; H, 2.41; N, 9.20%); ν_{max} (KBr, cm⁻¹) 3456m νO-H, 3254m νN-H, 3163m νArH, 1612s νC=N, 1544s νC-N, 1080s, 871s νC=S; ¹H NMR (DMSO) δ ppm 11.42 (1H, s, OH-Ar-CH=N-NH-), 10.25 (1H, s, OH-Ar-CH=N-CS-), 8.23 (1H, s, -HN-N=CH-Ar), 8.21 (1H, s, -CS-N=CH-Ar), 8.17 (1H, s, -HN-N=CH-Ar), 6.80-7.34 (6H, m, ArH).

N,N'-Bis(2-hydroxy-5-nitrobenzylidene)thiosemicarbazide (3) :

Thiosemicarbazide (0.072 g; 7.91 × 10⁻⁴ mol) was added to a dry THF (100 ml) solution of 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde (0.264 g; 15.80 × 10⁻⁴ mol). Compound (3) was obtained as like 1. Yellow-red solid, m.p. 127°, 0.215 g (69%) yield (Found : C, 46.01; H, 2.80; N, 17.11. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₁N₅O₆S : C, 46.27; H, 2.83; N, 17.99%); ν_{max} (KBr, cm⁻¹) 3423m νO-H, 3332m νN-H, 3070m νArH, 1627s νC=N, 1580s νC-N, 1095s, 838s νC=S; ¹H NMR (DMSO) δ ppm 11.53 (1H, s, OH-Ar-CH=N-NH-), 10.29 (1H, d, OH-Ar-CH=N-CS-, ³J_{CHNH} 2.85 Hz), 8.84 (1H, s, -HN-N=CH-Ar), 8.40 (1H, d, -CS-N=CH-Ar, ³J_{CHNH} 2.85 Hz), 8.34 (1H, s, -HN-N=CH-Ar), 7.02-8.28 (6H, m, Ar-H).

N,N'-Bis(2-oxo-1-naphthylidenemethylamino)thiosemicarbazide (4) :

Thiosemicarbazide (0.517 g; 5.67 × 10⁻³ mol) was added to a dry THF (100 ml) solution of 1-naphthaldehyde (1.954 g; 1.36 × 10⁻³ mol). Compound (4) was obtained as like 1. Yellow solid, m.p. 282°, 0.912 g (40%) yield (Found : C, 69.10; H, 4.20; N, 10.55. Calcd. for C₂₃H₁₇N₃O₂S : C, 69.20; H, 4.26; N, 10.50%); ν_{max} (KBr, cm⁻¹) 3451m νO-H, 3258m νN-H, 3167m νArH, 1626s νC=N, 1572s νC-N, 1032s, 882s νC=S; ¹H NMR (DMSO) δ ppm 11.40 (1H, s, OH-Ar-CH=N-NH-), 10.11 (1H, d, OH-Ar-CH=N-CS-, ³J_{CHNH} 7.38 Hz), 9.04 (1H, s, -HN-N=CH-Ar), 8.52 (1H, d, -CS-N=CH-Ar, ³J_{CHNH} 7.38 Hz), 8.23 (1H, s, -HN-N=CH-Ar), 7.19-7.90 (12H, m, ArH).

General method for preparation of [ML₁]₂ and [ML₁] complexes (M = Mn^{II} (1a), Co^{II} (1b), Ni^{II} (1c), Cu^{II} (1d), Zn^{II} (1e) and Hg^{II} (1f); H₂L₁ is the Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde with thiosemicarbazide :

A solution of metal(II) chloride (1 mmol) in methanol (50 ml) was mixed with a solution of the appropriate ligand (1 mmol) in methanol (50 ml) and heated for 75 min. The reaction mixture was cooled slowly and the solid product

formed was filtered, washed several times with methanol and dried.

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